

PPiPL

PLASTIC PACKAGING IN PEOPLE'S LIVES

Plastic Packaging in People's Lives Malaysia Pilot: Household and Waste Management Practices

Lancaster University
Management School

UK Research
and Innovation

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Glossary and Key Terms

3Rs - Reduce, Reuse, Recycle.

Act 672 - Shorthand for the 2007 Solid Waste Management and Public Cleansing Act.

Act 673 - Shorthand for the 2007 Solid Waste Management and Public Cleansing Corporation Act.

Circular economy - A term used by various stakeholders with slight variations to emphasise a holistic approach to reducing plastic pollution by considering impacts and activities throughout the entire lifecycle, both before and after consumption. This approach involves retaining resources through circular systems of reuse and recycling, rather than disposal.

Closed-loop recycling/system - A policy term that denotes the use of recycled material to remanufacture the same product that the material was used for previously (e.g. recycled HDPE from milk bottles to make milk bottles again). The term 'closed-loop system' is sometimes used to refer to a discrete assemblage of companies and organisations that work together along the value chain to collect, sort, and reprocess polymer material so that it can be returned to the same products.

Downcycling - A term used to refer to the process of recycling materials into applications that are of lower quality or value compared to the original product particularly in relation to their ability to be recycled again.

Dry market - A market selling clothing, electronics rather than fresh produce.

EPR - Extended Producer Responsibility.

Formal waste sector - Public or private sector corporations and registered businesses with capital investment, technological equipment and an organised labour force governed by labour laws.

halal rPET - Food-grade recycled Polyethylene Terephthalate in accordance with the 1983 Food Act and Halal certification standards.

HDPE - High-Density Polyethylene: a thermoplastic polymer known for its high strength-to-density ratio produced from the monomer ethylene.

Informal waste sector - Unregistered and unregulated waste collection and processing operations by individuals or small-scale businesses using labour intensive methods, local resources, and with low capital investment.

ISO 22000 - Sets out requirements for food safety management and can be certified.

LDPE - Low-Density Polyethylene: a thermoplastic produced from the monomer ethylene.

MPSR - Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap 2021-2030.

Multilayered material - Packaging made from more than one polymer (or other material), with additional material layers, components or adhesives that make separation and reprocessing more complex.

MYR - Malaysian Ringgit, currency of Malaysia.

NGO/s - Non-Governmental Organisation/s.

Non-Act state - A state that has not signed up to Act 672.

NRP - National Recycling Programme, Malaysia.

PET - Polyethylene Terephthalate: the most common thermoplastic polymer resin of the polyester family.

Plastic waste mismanagement - Plastic waste that has been improperly handled, sorted or disposed of, including mixing recyclables with general waste, dumping in unsanitary landfills or water bodies, and open burning.

PPE - Personal Protective Equipment.

PP - Polypropylene: a thermoplastic polymer produced from the monomer propylene.

Semi-informal waste sector - Organisations that are partially regulated waste collection and processing operations by individuals or small-scale businesses using labour intensive methods, local resources, and with low capital investment.

SUP - Single-Use Plastics.

SUPP - Single-Use Plastic Packaging.

SWCorp - Solid Waste and Public Cleansing Management Corporation.

Tailgate recycling - A practice that occurs at the back of the collection lorry, where a worker stands on the tail lift and separates valuable materials (such as plastics and cardboard) from the general waste bin bags thrown in by other workers.

Upcycling - A term used to refer to the process of transforming waste materials into applications of a greater quality or value compared to the original product, such as artistic or environmental value.

Wet market - A market selling fresh meat, fish, and produce.

WM - Waste Management

Executive Summary

Plastics play a critical role in society and the economy in Malaysia. Plastic pollution has sparked debate about waste management, its environmental impact, and health consequences.

The Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap (MPSR) 2021-2030¹ was developed to support the phasing out of unnecessary single-use packaging, recyclability and reusability, improve recycling collection rates, and meet food-grade recycled polyethylene terephthalate (halal rPET) standards by the end of the decade.

In a twelve-month pilot project, our team explored household and waste management practices in Malaysia, revealing:

- + Potential challenges.
- + Opportunities to support the MPSR ambitions.
- + Future research directions to implement actionable initiatives to reduce plastic usage and waste.

Key challenges

Against the backdrop of government policies, voluntary initiatives and market activities, our research highlights six key challenges.

+ Plastic packaging overconsumption

- Efforts to reduce plastic consumption have had limited impact, hampered by the persistent overuse of LDPE bags, the rise in waste generated by convenience-driven practices, and the lasting impact of COVID-19 pandemic-related delivery services.

+ Plastics delayed from entering waste streams

- Eradicating harmful plastic packaging may be delayed due to widespread positive attitudes and practices around re-using and repurposing plastics. The challenge is to balance the efficient recapture of plastic waste into appropriate waste streams, while also promoting reuse and repurposing of plastics.

+ Lack of clear guidance about waste practices

- Due to lack of clear guidance and infrastructure, households often rely on their own heuristics and judgements to separate waste (often dividing waste into just two categories – wet and dry), leaving further sorting to waste collectors or pickers.

+ Infrastructure for plastic recycling

- There is a fragmented infrastructure to support responsible separation at source, and consumers place responsibility on manufacturers, waste management and school education to provide information.

+ Capturing quality plastic packaging recyclables

- The quality and quantity of collecting and sorting plastic packaging varies significantly by recycling centre size. The variety in practices, including financial incentives, contributes to contamination and the inability to monitor waste material flows.

+ Navigating the intricacies of regulated and unregulated practices

- Operating without regulation provides flexibility in waste management systems but also contributes to inadequate waste infrastructures, recyclable material losses and illegal practices.

Opportunities

The challenges present four clear opportunities to reduce plastic packaging consumption, enhance recycling, and improve both material quality and data collection.

OPPORTUNITY 1: REDUCE CONSUMPTION OF SINGLE-USE PLASTICS	OPPORTUNITY 2: ENHANCING CONSUMER EDUCATION ON RECYCLING PRACTICES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Consumer empowerment + Reduce plastic packaging use + Awareness training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Clearer labelling + Public awareness campaigns + Accessible resources
OPPORTUNITY 3: IMPROVE MATERIAL QUALITY BY REDUCING CONTAMINATION	OPPORTUNITY 4: IMPROVE DATA COLLECTION AND TRANSPARENCY FROM RECYCLING COLLECTION FACILITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Education and Training + Improve collection and sorting + Collaboration to address waste material mismanagement + Supporting a circular economy + Recognising informal recyclers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Staff training + Data transparency

Implications for the Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap 2021-2030

Our research aligns with the MPSR ambitions, focusing on challenges and opportunities to reduce plastic packaging consumption, improve recycling, material quality and data collection.

MALAYSIAN PLASTIC SUSTAINABILITY ROADMAP TARGETS	← PPIPL Responses →	
	ACTIONS	OUTCOMES & RESOURCES
Phase out unnecessary single-use plastics	Obtained detailed insights into consumer behaviour and from waste management organisations and workers	8 organisations and 10 households took part in this study
25% of post-consumer plastic packaging to be recycled 100% recyclability of plastic packaging 15% average recycled content 76% collected for recycling rate	Create guidance for post-consumption organisations	Industry and policy: Household and waste management practices report 54 Degrees Not the enemy - Taking PPIPL international Public: Pilot project Malaysia infographic
Post-consumer halal rPET standard by 2022	Out of scope ²	Out of scope ²

Future research

To support the MPSR's ambitions, immediate research agendas emerge to:

- + Rethink the consumer attitude behaviour gap to support behavioural shifts to reduce plastic packaging consumption and enhance recycling practices.
- + Map circular material and social flows and fates for plastic packaging recycling to support high-quality material recapture.
- + Digital monitoring of material flows, focusing on the role of technologies in collecting and recording recycling rates, aiming to improve data collection, transparency and inclusivity.

The methodology

This was a twelve-month pilot project with a limited sample size (10 households, 8 organisations). The project used a range of research methods to gather insights to drive meaningful change towards more sustainable packaging practices, including:

A literature review.

In-depth interviews.

Household ethnographies.

Site visits with waste experts and representatives.

Context

Plastic in Malaysia

Plastic production plays a crucial role in Malaysia's economy contributing to nearly 5% of national Gross Domestic Product in 2018³. The Malaysian plastic market is estimated to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 3.9% in the period 2024-2029⁴. However, despite the industry's economic significance, plastic recycling and waste management represent significant challenges in Malaysia.

Approximately, 81% of the value is lost for four of the main plastic types consumed in Malaysia, including:

- + Polyethylene terephthalate (PET).
- + Polypropylene (PP).
- + High-density polyethylene (HDPE).
- + Low-density polyethylene (LDPE).

This loss is a result of poor material quality, low collection rates, contamination, and inefficient recycling infrastructures³. These material losses mean plastic recyclers depend on imported plastic because it is cheaper and guarantees a steady supply³.

The dramatic rise in plastic waste imports, particularly following China's 2018 plastic waste ban^{5,6}, has exacerbated the waste management and recycling issues. Despite the Malaysian government's efforts to close more than 140 illegal plastic recycling plants⁷, illegal dumping and unregulated recycling operations persist due to the sheer volume of plastic waste⁸. These illegal activities, often involving subcontracted factories, further complicate the country's waste management landscape. While plastic waste imports have declined slightly since 2018, Malaysia remains one of the world's largest importers of plastic waste.

Single-use plastics (SUP) and single-use plastic packaging (SUPP) represent the largest segment of Malaysia's plastic market¹⁰ equating to 48% of the total production of plastics³. In humid climates like Malaysia, plastic packaging is essential for preserving food quality, safety, and freshness. Alternatives such as paper packaging often perform poorly in these conditions, as they absorb moisture, potentially compromising food integrity and increasing unnecessary food waste.

Despite its practicality and commercial success, plastic packaging (especially SUP) creates long-term environmental damage. Due to the difficulties in recycling, mismanaged plastics frequently end up polluting land and marine ecosystems, causing long-term ecological harm^{11,12}.

Malaysia is reported to be one of the largest producers of mismanaged plastic waste with an estimated 370 million kilograms entering watercourses annually^{3,13}. Plastic pollution has far-reaching consequences, not only for biodiversity but also for key economic spheres including tourism, fishing, and shipping¹⁰. It is estimated that the future cost of removing plastic pollution from the environment is projected to exceed the cost of preventing littering and plastic waste mismanagement today¹⁰. Critically, the growing body of evidence on the human health impacts of plastic pollution, especially microplastics, underscores the urgency of addressing the issue^{10,14}.

The immediate need to reduce total waste generation is evident from Malaysia's population growth, increasing consumption patterns, and landfill sites nearing maximum capacity¹³.

To address these challenges, the Malaysian government introduced the Plastics Sustainability Roadmap 2021-2030 (MPSR)¹ stipulating ambitions by 2030 to:

Phase out unnecessary single-use plastics.

25% of post-consumer plastic packaging to be recycled by 2025.

100% recyclability of plastic packaging.

15% average recycled content.

76% collected for-recycling rate.

Post-consumer halal rPET standard by 2022.

To address plastic packaging effectively, solutions could include:

Improving identification mechanisms.

Implementing Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR).

Empowering the informal sector.

Strengthening public-private-informal collaboration.

Enhancing waste recovery systems.

Increasing material (re)utilisation and recognition of its economic value.

Awareness training and communication.

However, without a thorough understanding of the practical challenges faced by both consumers and waste management organisations, decision-making processes and solution implementation may not be successful.

Government initiatives relevant to single-use plastic packaging

The statutory responsibilities for waste management in Malaysia are set out in numerous roadmaps, policies and initiatives. These have emerged over the past thirty years and aim to encourage responsible consumption and production to reduce waste.

1993

In 1993, the National Recycling Programme (NRP) initiative was launched to encourage citizens to apply the 3Rs - Reduce, Reuse and Recycle¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The NRP aimed to improve solid waste management through recycling and disposal, and concessionary responsibilities attached with collection, storage, treatment, and recycling of non-hazardous waste. During this period federalisation and privatisation of waste management occurred¹⁸. However, the NRP was not fully realised until 2015^{19,20}. The uptake of the 3Rs was limited and culminated in a relaunch of the NRP at the end of 2000¹⁵⁻¹⁷ combined with the development of the Eighth Malaysia Plan for 2001-2005.

By 2006, the Waste Minimization Master Plan was introduced to enhance awareness, collaborations, and partnerships surrounding waste minimisation¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

2006

2001

The Eighth Malaysia Plan aimed to instil recycling habits, reduce operational costs, minimise landfill waste volumes, reduce utilisation of raw materials, and improve awareness and cooperation among stakeholders²¹. In addition, in 2001, the Ministry of Housing and Local Government Malaysia launched the annual National Recycling Day on 11th November^{16,22}.

2002

The National Strategic Plan for solid waste management was formulated in 2002 and adopted in 2005²³. The plan expanded the waste management hierarchy from three steps to a five-step process (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Treatment and Disposal).

2011

Since 2011, momentum has gathered surrounding SUPs, with various initiatives and strategic and action plans being developed. Examples include: the nationwide “No Plastic Bag Day” campaign²⁵ banning free plastic bags at grocery stores and supermarkets and adding a 0.20MY levy per bag; the SWCorp Strategy plan 2014-2020²⁶ to further promote sustainable waste management; and, the Comprehensive Action Plan of Solid Waste Management 2015-2020¹⁷. These initiatives aimed to raise public awareness and improve consumer behaviour, in conjunction with improving recycling facilities and strengthening government-private collaborations.

2014 → 2020

2015 → 2020

2021 → 2030

2021 → 2025

The MPSR 2021-2030¹, National Marine Litter Policy and Action Plan 2021-2030³⁰, and the Twelfth Malaysia Plan 2021-2025³¹ all emphasise circular economy solutions, waste reduction, reduce pollution, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) implementation, and increase recycled material use. Currently, the National Solid Waste Management Department, which is under the Ministry of Housing and Local Government, is responsible for plastic waste management in Malaysia¹⁸.

2030

2007

Waste and public cleansing management was standardised in 2007 through the Solid Waste and Public Cleansing Management Act 672²⁴ to encourage household waste management, mandatory separation at source, recovery of recyclable materials and to extend the operating capacity of landfill sites. In conjunction with Act 672, the Solid Waste Management and Public Cleansing Management Corporation Act 673 was introduced to establish governance that would be overseen by the National Solid Waste Management Department and Solid Waste and Public Cleansing Management Corporation (SWCorp).

2020

Between 2016-2020, the government established waste-to-energy incineration plants, outlined in the Tenth and Eleventh Malaysia Plans^{20,27}. In accordance with the Malaysia's Roadmap towards Zero Single-Use Plastics 2018-2030, pollution charges would be imposed on consumers and manufacturers of SUPs²⁸, triggering three federal territories in 2019 to ban plastic straws^{13,29}. In 2020, a statewide ban was implemented but has yet to be enforced.

Waste management in Malaysia

Waste management is a fragmented system with formal, semi-formal and informal operations playing significant roles^{13,32,33}.

Formal waste operations

Consists of registered and licenced public or private sector corporations with capital investment, technological equipment and an organised labour force, governed by labour laws but handling only a small fraction of domestic plastic, collecting 0.09% of it^{33,34}.

In contrast, semi-formal and informal operations, are more actively involved in waste collection sorting and recycling practices, particularly for high-value plastics like PET, HDPE, PP and LDPE³.

Semi-formal waste operations

Involve partially regulated waste collection and processing activities, undertaken by individuals or small-scale businesses, using labour intensive methods, local resources, and with low capital investment.

Informal waste operations

Comprise of unregistered and unregulated waste collection and processing operations by individuals or small-scale businesses using labour intensive methods, local resources, and with low capital investment^{13,15}.

These informal recyclers often operate outside formal systems, contributing to higher recycling rates^{13,15}, but complicating efforts to improve sustainability and control pollution.

The key stakeholders in Malaysia's waste management system include^{13, 15, 33}:

- + Waste pickers.
- + Itinerant buyers.
- + Micro-enterprises.
- + Non-Governmental Organisation (NGOs).
- + Small recycling centres.
- + Formal recycling companies.

CURRENT

NOT TO SCALE ³

IDEAL

The Pilot Project

Plastic Packaging in People's Lives (PPiPL) Malaysia Pilot

Plastic Packaging in People's Lives (PPiPL) Malaysia Pilot is a collaborative research project between Lancaster University and Sunway University, involving a team of 12 researchers and six research assistants with expertise spanning consumer insights, psychology, waste, inequality, and material science.

Launched in 2022, the project ran between October 2022 to September 2023 focusing on the Selangor state in Malaysia.

The project aimed to provide an in-depth understanding of plastic packaging consumption and disposal. This study integrated an analysis of how plastic use intersects with the personal, professional, and social activities of selected Malaysian households, as well as the waste management systems these households operate within.

The multi-disciplinary team gathered these insights to help guide industry professionals and policymakers, emphasising cultural and behavioural norms surrounding plastic use.

This pilot research has:

- + Identified challenges: including plastic packaging overconsumption, consumer resistance to changing food packaging, to the complexities of navigating regulated and unregulated practices.
- + Uncovered opportunities: for reducing plastic packaging consumption and encouraging the recapture of materials for recycling.
- + Revealed a research agenda: providing a focus for follow-up future research.

Research design

The research followed a two-phase approach:

- + Household research: that collected data from desk-based research, household ethnographies and in-depth interviews.
- + Waste management research: including in-depth interviews and site visits with waste experts and representatives.

The research

Funded by the UKRI Global Challenges Research Fund and Newton Consolidation Accounts and Lancaster Future Cities Research Institute, academics from Lancaster and Sunway universities explored:

Household research

Before fieldwork commenced, a context document was developed, detailing key demographic and economic statistics for Malaysia. This included population data, urbanisation trends, household types, income levels, and specific insights into Selangor. This document provided a foundation that ensured a representative selection of households was made for the study (the **context** is summarised on page 23).

The table below presents details of the household categories investigated. All participants were heads of their households, aged 18 or older, and held primary responsibility for food purchase and household duties. A combination of purposive and snowball sampling methods³⁵ was employed for recruitment, leveraging online platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter to identify and engage participants.

Household types for PPIPL Malaysia Pilot research project³⁶.

Type of household	Single person household	Lone young adult of age under 35, unmarried without children
	Single person household	Lone person of age over 50
	Two person household	Couples without children
	Three to five persons household	Nuclear family, 2 parents and 1 or 2 children
	Two to three persons household	Lone parent with 1 or 2 independent children
	Two to three persons household	Lone parent with 1 or 2 dependent children
	Extended family household	Parents, children and grandparent(s) or other relative(s) living together in rural area
	Multiple household	Members of household are not related (e.g. student accommodation)

Fieldwork with 10 households, conducted between February 21 to March 30, 2023, used a multi-sited ethnographic approach³⁵ to explore consumers' daily interactions with food packaging and waste management. Researchers employed in-depth interviews, household tours, and participant diaries to capture the lived experiences of participants regarding plastic packaging and household waste practices. Key topics explored during the interviews included household routines, food consumption habits, plastic packaging use, and waste disposal behaviours.

Waste management research

The waste management research focused on understanding Malaysia's plastic packaging waste treatment, recycling rates, and the barriers to recycling. To support this phase, the team expanded the context document detailing plastic production, waste treatment processes, and recycling challenges in the country (see [summary](#) on pages 24-25). This document informed fieldwork conducted with both formal and informal waste management organisations.

The research involved eight formal, semi-formal and informal waste management locations, including six waste management organisations, one sanitary landfill site and one unregistered dumpsite. A total of twelve formal and twelve informal interviews were conducted with managers and workers. These interviews³⁵ focused on plastic waste collection, sorting, treatment, and recycling processes.

Interviews were conducted in multiple languages - English, Malay, Tamil, and Bangladeshi - with translation support provided by research assistants. However, some informal sector workers, particularly those from unregulated sites, were hesitant to participate, which limited the data collected from these groups. Fieldwork took place from February 21 to March 30, 2023, adopting a mobile ethnology inspired approach³⁷ that follows the action of the plastic packaging waste. Interviews typically lasted around 2.5 hours with managers and approximately 30 minutes with lower-level workers. Interviews were supplemented by site tours, during which the research team observed operations and collected additional data through field notes and photographs.

Data analysis

Data analysis for both the household and waste management research, was guided by key themes that emerged during the study³⁸. Initial themes were derived from the interview topics.

For the household research these included: everyday routines related to food provisioning; preparation and consumption; and, post-consumption practices involving plastic packaging. For the waste management research, the themes were: challenges in plastics recycling; collaboration with government; manufacturers and other waste management units; Act 672; material value; and, material flow. Additional insights emerged during analysis, including shifts in consumer behaviour post-COVID-19 and how these changes affected waste workers' daily routines, particularly in areas with contaminated water supplies, which increased reliance on PET water bottles.

The final analysis for the household research resulted in 12 primary themes and 38-sub-themes, while the waste management research identified 26 primary themes and 42 sub-themes. To synthesise findings from both phases, an integrative approach was employed, highlighting commonalities and discrepancies across the two areas.

The combined insights from both research phases offer a comprehensive understanding of the social, economic, and logistical factors that shape plastic packaging use and waste management in Selangor.

Study limitations

The data was collected from a small pool of participants and may not represent or reflect the perspectives of households, waste organisations or waste workers across Selangor. Additionally, this pilot study did not cover the intersections or relationships between the various government roadmaps and policies for managing waste and material resources.

The Selangor Plastic Packaging Landscape: Demographics, Economic Background and Waste Management

Selangor

Malaysia's most populous state.

21.6%

making up 21.6% of the national population in 2022

Family and birth rates

The state has high urbanisation with 62.6% of its population residing in Selangor itself, especially in Petaling, Hulu Langat and Klang districts⁴⁰. Selangor has the highest life expectancy in Malaysia (77.5 years), reflecting an increase in longevity despite a slight decline due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Life expectancy in Selangor is 76.1 years for males and 80.3 years for females³⁹.

Demographics

The population is diverse, with the majority being Bumiputera (69.9%), followed by Chinese (22.8%) and Indian (6.6%) communities. In terms of religious beliefs, 61.1% of citizens are Muslims, followed by 21.6% Buddhists, 10.3% Hindu, 4.9% Christians and 1.3% other religion. Less than 1% of citizens declare no belief³⁹.

Life expectancy

Selangor also recorded the highest number of live births in Malaysia in 2022 and a significant proportion of the population are married (61.6%), followed by those not married (34.4%) married, or divorced/separated (1.9%), especially in the Petaling district. Total fertility rate is 1.5 children which closely corresponds to overall Malaysian fertility rate of 1.6. The average family size of 3.6 persons in Selangor corresponds to the average size in Malaysia³⁹.

Economics

Economically, Malaysia is divided into three income groups: Top 20% (T20), Middle 40% (M40), and Bottom 40% (B40). Selangor has a relatively low poverty rate (6.2% in 2022)⁴¹, though a significant portion of Malaysia's B40 population (10.4%)⁴² resides in the state. Despite economic growth and urbanisation, income inequality remains a challenge, particularly for rural areas and the B40 demographic⁴².

Education

In terms of education, 28.4% (1.7 million) of all graduates in Malaysia are residents of Selangor⁴³. Nearly 88% of these graduates participate in labour force, most in services (76.7%), manufacturing (14.4%) and construction (5.7%) with 2.7% unemployed. Selangor statistics on poverty occurrence counts 1.5% in urban and 3.1% in rural regions for absolute poverty, and 14.2% in urban and 29.7% in rural areas for relative poverty⁴¹.

Selangor household waste management

Residents in Selangor are not required to separate their waste for recycling^{3, 17, 24, 44}. Due to the absence of household bins provided by waste management companies or local authorities, waste is usually placed in bags positioned in front of the gate or door. Waste collection options vary depending on the locality. Households decide whether plastic packaging will be disposed of as general waste (referred to as wet waste) or separated at source (referred to as dry waste).

Plastic packaging disposed of as general waste is collected either at specified dates and times, or upon request by residents. Waste collection is typically undertaken by formal or semi-formal waste management organisations. The collected waste is either transported to a sanitary landfill or illegal dumpsite, or is redirected to a recycling centre or junkyard through tailgate recycling.

Tailgate recycling occurs at the back of the collection lorry, where a worker stands on the tail lift and separates valuable materials (such as plastics and cardboard) from the general waste bin bags thrown in by other workers. These salvaged materials are sold to recycling centres.

At illegal dumpsites, waste pickers may extract usable materials, which are then sold to junkyards or recycling centres. However, waste pickers are generally not permitted at sanitary landfills for safety reasons.

At the recycling centre, waste undergoes further sorting into specific material categories and is processed to meet the requirements of material traders. This process may include shredding into different size pieces, squashing, or simply sorting and leaving the plastic packaging in its original form for sale.

Plastic packaging separated at source (household) follows various pathways, offering residents multiple options, including:

- + **Reuse in home.** Plastic packaging that is reused at home is diverted entirely away from the waste flow.
- + **Formal collections.** Formal scheduled collections are conducted on days separate from general waste collection and can also be arranged on demand.
- + **Informal collections by waste pickers.** Informal waste picker collections are arranged by the household.
- + **Collections and drop-offs to NGOs.** Households can either arrange collection by an NGO or drop-off to an NGO collection point.
- + **Drop-offs at community centres.** Community drop-off centres provide either supervised or unsupervised access, with some centres offering financial incentives based on weight, to encourage household recycling.

Plastic packaging collected through formal, informal, NGO collections and community drop-off centres is sent to formal and semi-formal recycling centres for further sorting and processing.

The process of monitoring and quality checking recyclables varies depending on the formality of each recycling centre. This ranges from, the use of advanced collector's applications and reward systems, to minimal or no monitoring at all.

Six Key Challenges

Efforts to reduce plastic consumption have had limited impact, hampered by the persistent overuse of LDPE bags, the rise in waste generated by convenience-driven practices, and the lasting impact of COVID-19 pandemic-related delivery services.

Eradicating harmful plastic packaging may be delayed due to widespread positive attitudes and practices around re-using and repurposing plastics. The challenge is to balance the efficient recapture of plastic waste into appropriate waste streams, while also promoting reuse and repurposing of plastics.

Due to lack of clear guidance and infrastructure, households often rely on their own heuristics and judgements to separate waste (often dividing waste into just two categories - wet and dry), leaving further sorting to waste collectors or pickers.

There is a fragmented infrastructure to support responsible separation at source, and consumers place responsibility on manufacturers, waste management and school education to provide information.

The quality and quantity of collecting and sorting plastic packaging varies significantly by recycling centre size. The variety in practices, including financial incentives, contribute to contamination and inability to monitor waste material flows.

Operating without regulation provides flexibility in waste management systems but also contributes to inadequate waste infrastructures, recyclable material losses and illegal practices.

Challenge 1: Plastic packaging overconsumption

Efforts to reduce plastic consumption have had limited impact, hampered by the persistent overuse of LDPE bags, the rise in waste generated by convenience-driven practices, and the lasting impact of COVID-19 pandemic-related delivery services.

Limited impact of the "No Plastic Bag Day" campaign

The "No Plastic Bag Day" campaign, later rebranded as "Bring Your Own Bag", launched in 2011²⁵ to reduce plastic bag consumption and had limited success. While it encouraged some customers to bring reusable carrier bags (due to the 0.20 MYR charge for plastic bags), many participants perceived the fee as a revenue-generating tactic by retailers rather than an environmental or Corporate Social Responsibility initiative. Customers preferred plastic bags over more expensive paper bags (RM 0.70), citing their reusability and higher load capacity.

“

If it's 99 Speedmart, then yes. Because...they don't give plastic bags. And they'll charge us for the bags. They'll charge 0.20 MYR. So usually, we'll bring our own bag.

(Saddie, 56, self-employed, extended family household)

“

... let's say if you buy fish or meats, then the paper bag will be like not practical. So still, a plastic bag is better for those uh, stuff.

(Delanie, 47, teacher, two to three persons household with independent children)

Continued use of LDPE bags

The “Bring Your Own Bag” campaign failed to reduce the use of LDPE bags, which remain widely distributed for free in shopping centres and are heavily utilised by households²⁵. Retailers often provide LDPE bags for each item purchased, reinforcing their overconsumption. Some households seek alternatives by shopping at local wet markets to minimise food packaging, though dry markets continue to favour plastic packaging for hygiene and post-pandemic safety reasons.

“

If you go [to]... wet market or grocery shop, you'll bring back at least five [LDPE bags]. Last time, when we opened our reusable bag and asked them to put in... they are even more troublesome than... put[ting] in the plastic.

(Sally, 50, self-employed, single person household)

“

I use them [plastic bags] as garbage bag. I don't buy garbage bags

(Tina, 47, part-time lecturer, two to three persons household with dependent children)

Supermarket practices driving plastic use

Supermarkets contribute to overconsumption by using LDPE bags as alternatives to disposable Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) gloves, especially for handling fresh food. LDPE bags provided protection, and easier and quicker to use than putting on gloves. Households frequently reuse these bags, particularly as bin liners.

“

In the market they do pack it...in a single plastic. Yeah, we do bring our own bag, but then they pack their stuff in the plastics. So, there's like double plastic there. We just like take, take, take, and then they just pack, and then they just throw it in the plastic... They do provide plastic [bags] for free, so that's why they keep giving us plastic, if they charge, then we can stop that. But if not, then they keep giving...

(Naomi, 58, admin assistant, three to five persons household with children)

Increased plastic waste during the COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic saw a rise in plastic waste^{45,46}, with food delivery services introducing significant quantities of LDPE bags, PP containers, and plastic cutlery. While some participants opted for supermarket deliveries to mitigate risk, most used food and parcel delivery services for convenience, leading to increased packaging waste entering households. Even home meal preparation did not offset the surge in plastic consumption during lockdowns.

Many participants highlighted the time and cost-saving benefits of delivery services, both for food and non-food items, despite concerns about waste generation and sustainability.

“

So that time [during pandemic] I felt worried, until we find out that we can buy online. So that time we buy all the ingredients, the grocery, everything online. So, fruits, vegetables, fish, meat, we will buy online.

(Delanie, 47, teacher, two to three persons household with independent children)

Challenge 2: Plastics delayed from entering waste streams

Eradicating harmful plastic packaging may be delayed due to widespread positive attitudes and practices around re-using and repurposing plastics. The challenge is to balance the efficient recapture of plastic waste into appropriate waste streams, while also promoting reuse and repurposing of plastics.

Reusing plastic food containers and plastic bags (provided by most supermarkets free of charge) is a very common practice in the households who participated in this research. This practice is connected to food safety and freshness. Decisions to keep plastic packaging are based on their quality, cleanliness (e.g. ability to wash) and reuse potential. The potential for reuse at recycling centres is curtailed by domestic reuse as the packaging is delayed from entering the waste management systems or can be redirected to general waste.

LDPE bags

From fresh food purchases such as bread rolls, fruit and vegetables, where the products are individually bagged.

Plastic bags collected and reused in households.

Mostly reused once as bin liners, especially if they are dirty or hard to clean, entering general waste rather than recycling.

Resealable bags

From packaged coffee, refrigerated or dry foods sold in pouches.

Used to keep vegetables fresh or protect dry foods like fruit, nuts, and muesli. Often multilayered plastic packaging made from more than one polymer (or other materials such as aluminium foil), with additional material layers, components or adhesives.

PP containers

From items such as butter, ice cream, and cookies.

Repurposed for storing food in cupboards, fridges, or freezers.

Additionally, PP boxes from food delivery services are washed and reused, often referred to as "Tupperware" by participants (although they are not real Tupperware products).

Polystyrene cooler boxes

From refrigerated food deliveries, such as seafood.

Commonly used for seafood delivery. Despite the large size and single-use nature, some households repurpose these for composting or as plant pots, particularly for "wet" waste (e.g. fruit and vegetable peels, eggshells) to avoid odours in regular bins.

This practice is viewed as cost-effective and practical, especially in the face of expensive composting machines.

“

But the issue of polystyrene is as you know 90% air and 10% will be recycled. But it is bulky it takes so much of space. But if you are compacting it, it's fine... There are two companies over here in Malaysia... they also compact it, pack it, and make into photo frame...plastic is recyclable but since there is no value like polystyrene...

(Senen, Head of Facilities, Circular Economy Agenda)

Challenge 3: Lack of clear guidance about waste practices

Due to lack of clear guidance and infrastructure, households often rely on their own heuristics and judgements to separate waste (often dividing waste into just two categories – wet and dry), leaving further sorting to waste collectors or pickers.

Awareness and knowledge of waste material separation are crucial for improving recycling rates^{17,44}. Consumers often face confusion and uncertainty about where specific materials should be disposed of, compounded by a lack of clear instructions on product packaging, limited (household) space, time, and appropriate equipment (bins) for separation.

For some, separating waste at the source is seen as the "right thing to do", but improper handling (e.g. not rinsing, or squashing) can lead to contamination of recyclable materials redirecting waste to landfill.

In practice, households developed their own methods for distinguishing and separating different waste categories. The most common approach involved using sensory cues, particularly touch, to identify materials and assign them to specific categories (e.g. soft plastics versus hard plastics). However, some participants opted for broader categories, grouping items as plastics (anything that looks or feels like plastic), paper, glass, cans, or simply separating waste into "wet" and "dry" categories. This approach highlights a lack of standardised guidance and the reliance on intuitive or "common-sense" methods, which may contribute to inefficiency and improper recycling.

“

I will separate in... Wet and dry. I'm not specific like paper or plastic because I don't want to [separate] waste [into] the plastic, because sometimes it is wet, just a little. Then the dry one like something like packaging, all the, how to say, the box, or our delivery, the grocery one, big box. Yeah, then the packaging outside the plastic. That one can consider clean, dry. Then I can keep it until the plastic bags [are] full, then I only can take [them] out. So, the wet one I will uh, I will throw out every day, ...because it will smell. Bin is here. This one is our wet bin, that one inside is the dry one. This one is a reuse bag.”

(Lola, 35, banking, two persons household without children)

Challenge 4: Infrastructure for plastic recycling

There is a fragmented infrastructure to support responsible separation at source and consumers place responsibility on manufacturers, waste management and school education to provide information.

Recycling services and facilities are not universally available, and for households there is a general sense of uncertainty and scepticism regarding the recycling system.

Some consumers are highly motivated to recycle and actively seek information to improve their separation practices. However, the method of household waste separation is often influenced by the preferences and requirements of local waste collectors, both formal and informal. As a result, many households adjust their separation practices to align with these collectors, which impacts the quality of the materials collected and determines where the waste ultimately ends up.

“

They just drive a big lorry and then everything [is] throw[n] in together. So, no matter how you separate it.

(Jared, 35, lecturer, two persons household without children)

“

Uh, actually, I'm waiting for the charity organisation to come to collect. When they come, they can take everything. But if they don't come, I will, depend[ing] on [the] items, give to the waste collector...it's a regular contact... They also recycle...for them they will make money from the recycl[abl]e[s]. So, they are willing to help. Yeah... it's for their good as well, somehow. I think it's a win-win situation. For me, at least I don't throw it in general waste.

(Sally, 50, self-employed, single person household)

It is often rare for plastic food packaging in Malaysia to include guidance or indicators on how to correctly dispose of it or what type of materials they are manufactured from. When labels are present, they often focus on quality standards (e.g. "Food Safety Management" or ISO 22000), which can lead to confusion.

The lack of clear or up-to-date information on disposal is one of the key reasons consumers discard packaging with general waste instead of recycling it properly. Consumers placed the responsibility with manufacturers, waste management, government, or school education to provide guidance.

“

The key is actually the education. Education, yes. We must - all these things can be done when we are well trained, uh, in the school. And the school, for example, like, primary school level when we have the teaching. Trust me, everybody will remember them when you learn them every other day. All the way towards your primary to your secondary I tell you; you will remember them for life.

(Rumi, 50, IT Specialist, three to five persons household with children)

“

What we have here? This one? ISO 22000... Okay. It's the - it's the only one... You know, if it's like this, people cannot really understand really. And ISO doesn't even tell you what kind of packaging it is. It's very hard for people to participate in recycling.

(Amy, 46, teacher, extended family household)

Challenge 5: Capturing quality plastic packaging recyclables

The quality and quantity of collecting and sorting plastic packaging varies significantly by recycling centre size. The variety in practices, including financial incentives, contribute to contamination and inability to monitor waste material flows.

Quality over quantity

The most valuable plastic packaging types include HDPE, PET, LDPE, and PP³. These were accepted by all recycling centres participating in our research. The procedure of monitoring or checking material quality varied and corresponded to the level of formality of each recycling centre.

Smaller and formal recycling centres and collection points

The focus is on material quality, investing time and money to check recyclables upon arrival. These centres educate consumers about the types and physical appearance of plastics, recycling at home and providing them with bins/bags and/or money for their waste.

Larger and semi-informal/informal recycling centres

Accept all materials regardless of their condition or origin.

The quality preferred in small recycling centres is linked to financial value, environmental impact and opportunities for upcycling. However, waste management companies often use contractors for waste transport, limiting their control over material distribution.

Contractors can take the material to any recycling centre, whether formal or informal, or to landfill. This type of waste management recreates disparities between formal and informal recycling sites in terms of quality and quantity of materials received.

Plastic waste mismanagement is primarily due to market prices, limited budgets and time spent by collection workers on their daily routes. Contamination of recyclables is a key challenge and there are numerous points from household through to recycling that this can occur. A significant source of contamination was the practice of tailgate recycling where plastic packaging was removed from the general waste discarded from households at the point of collection.

Multilayered materials and bioplastics contribute to the amount of waste ending up in Malaysian landfills. Managers of formal waste management companies emphasised the importance of EPR legislation^{1.3} as a mechanism to tackle the issues and avoid downcycling materials. The onus was placed on brand owners to better communicate with manufacturers and recyclers and pay extra money for hard to recycle products.

“

The problem we face is that some of the contractors have limited time because when they send the domestic waste to the landfill, they can queue up to 2 or 3 hours at the landfill just to drop the domestic waste because there's a lot of [other lorries]. So, what they do is they try to drop any of the recycling that they see along the way... Some of what they call this recycling site are illegal. They don't pay the license and everything and all, but they can offer a little bit more than what we can offer. The price in the market is one of the problems. So, whoever can provide more then they will go there.

(Mahadi, Assistant Manager, Recycling Centre I)

“

Normally the garbage is sorted by the workers before they come in but there will still be garbage in it. We will sort it and put it in front. Later we will ask our trucks to take it to landfill.

(Kassim, Gate Guard/Site Supervisor, Recycling Centre II)

Incentivising collections: “Trash for cash”

Various semi-formal and informal recycling centres, waste pickers, and some NGOs and community drop-off centres, offer cash for the delivery of recyclable materials. However, this encourages certain participants to focus on separating - the most profitable - types of plastic packaging, rather than sorting all the different types of waste, including plastics, at source. Most semi-formal and informal recycling units accept materials regardless of quality and cleanliness.

Similarly, some waste collection workers, who are usually contractors for formal waste management organisations, participate in “trash for cash” through tailgate recycling practices. The materials are usually sold to informal recycling plants or junkyards, where the price is higher because some of the informal businesses do not pay for any licences and can offer more money for the materials. For these usually low paid workers, tailgate recycling brings extra income.

“

I will sell it as a scrap to the scrap collectors. Same goes to the plastic bottles and papers because there are certain values there. So that is the only reason why we actually separate them. Separating the plastic bottles and papers.

(Rumi, 50, IT specialist, three to five persons household with children)

JOM KITA SEMULA!
"Waste is not dirty, waste is money"

JENIS SISA KITAR SEMULA & HARGA

	HARGA/UNIT
M3 Majalah/Novel/Kertas Campur.....	RM0.20/Kg
M2 Kotak.....	RM0.30/Kg
M4 Besi.....	RM0.35/Kg
M1 Surat Khabar.....	RM0.45/Kg
M3 Kertas Hitam Putih.....	RM0.20/Kg
M6 Plastik.....	RM0.40/Kg
M5 Tin Aluminium.....	RM2.20/Kg
M7 Minyak Masak Terpakai.....	RM1.50/Kg

*Harga belian tertakluk kepada harga semasa

SISA ELEKTRONIK / E-WASTE

Printer/Microwave.....	RM0.30/Kg
CD-ROM/UPS/AVR.....	RM0.30/Kg
Mesin Pengimbas/Fax.....	RM0.30/Kg
Vacuum.....	RM0.30/Kg
Camera.....	RM0.30/Kg
CD/DVD.....	RM0.30/Kg
Mesin Fotostat.....	RM0.42/Kg
Bateri kereta.....	RM0.90/Kg
Penghawa Dingin.....	RM1.20/Kg
Server.....	RM1.20/Kg
Mix Wire/ Power Cable.....	RM0.70/Kg
Hard Disk.....	RM2.50/Kg
Smart Phone/Tablet.....	RM5.00/Kg
Motherboard/IC Board.....	RM10.00/Kg
Monitor/Tv/Laptop.....	RM3.00/Unit
CPU.....	RM5.00/Unit
Mesin Basuh.....	RM4.00/Unit
Peti Sejuk.....	RM4.00/Unit
Compressor.....	RM1.20/Kg

*Harga belian tertakluk kepada harga semasa

Nikmati ganjaran wang tunai dengan menjual barangan kitar semula anda di Pusat Kitar Semula Cyberjaya

TOGETHER WE KEEP SELANGOR CLEAN!

“

We will weigh the recyclable items and pay them. We don't partner with anyone [apart from one contractor]. But there are sometimes people come in and sell the recycling items which is from households. I take care of the workers and pay to the people who comes in and sell the recycling items. I would say that [contractor's name] lorry comes in and say that they have sorted the plastics out before they come and sell. But they still put in some garbage to make it look heavier so that they get more money. So, it gets hard for us to pay them. [The most profitable item is] HDPE plastics.

(Kassim, Gate Guard/ Site Supervisor, Recycling Centre II)

Challenge 6: Navigating the intricacies of regulated and unregulated practices

Operating without regulation provides flexibility for waste management systems but also contributes to inadequate waste infrastructures, recyclable material losses and illegal practices.

The 2007 Solid Waste Management and Public Cleansing Management (Act 672)

Not all states have signed up to the 2007 Solid Waste Management and Public Cleansing Management, known as Act 672.

Operating a waste management company in a state without Act 672 (non-Act state) has both advantages and disadvantages.

	Non-act	Act signed
Governance	Freedom of self-management	Regulations and commitments, the same rules for everyone
Financial sources	Less financial sources, dependence on local councils, amount, and quality of sold material and fundings	Government secures financial sources
Tailgate recycling	Allowed	Not allowed
Services	WM company can provide wider range of services (seeing the whole picture of what service is needed)	Services provided according to the licence
Data management	No unification, some data not available	Unification of system brings comparable data on waste and recycling materials
Public education	WM company's responsibility	Education of public provided by the state
Infrastructure	No bins/containers for recyclables provided (unless WM company decides to invest in them)	Bins/containers for recyclables provided by the state government

The Selangor region is a non-Act state.

Non-Act state: Advantages

Managers of formal waste management companies find that not adhering to Act 672 provides them with greater operational flexibility, particularly in sales of recyclable materials and acquisition strategies. In addition, reward systems offered by waste companies to customers (e.g. points and discount for waste collection, vouchers) and collectors (e.g. "trash for cash") are not state regulated, allowing flexibility in pricing and incentives.

A significant number of households struggle to afford necessities such as food and accommodation (10.4% of B40 low-income population category reside in Selangor). Remaining a non-Act state allows opportunities for additional income through options such as "trash for cash", potentially encouraging residents to recycle plastic packaging. Signing up to the legislation could shift attention to waste management and reinforce the income gap in Selangor.

Non-Act state: Disadvantages

States without Act 672 receive fewer federal financial resources, resulting in inadequate infrastructure, such as lack of household recycling bins or containers and infrequent or non-existent recycling collections. The reliance on funding provided by city, municipal or district councils tends to prioritise the quantity of materials over quality, leading to contamination of recyclables.

Signing Act 672

The signing of Act 672 by the Selangor region could unify waste management and recycling systems, potentially increasing transparency³. Improved governance of waste management systems could bring reliable and comparable data, improve material quality, decrease mismanagement of waste, and provide better education and knowledge sharing for consumers³. However, consideration and open dialogues would need to occur to ensure residents, formal/semi-formal/informal waste organisations and workers are not disadvantaged.

“

Because when we are not under the federal act, then we cannot tap into federal resources, is as simple as that, right. So, of course those states that signed Act 672, they can get resources. More resources actually from the federal government... Now, the minute you sign, you must give away your right. You have no more control. So, the control will go to the federal government.

(Senen, Head of Facilities, Circular Economy Agenda Organisation)

“

...with the correct amount of data, if we know, and it is regulated, if a certain authority or agency says okay Malaysia can generate this amount of plastic bottles, let's have this programme locally, and they can sell it locally or they can export it elsewhere no issue. Then we can... spur up the economy to the creating that from the whole cycle from the usage, collection, the processing, and then the manufacturing it and putting it back in the same cycle, and it's still in the same country. Or even if it's outside at least that value is already been invested back again into the country...[without the data] we cannot have a complete picture on this.

(Hashim, Assistant Manager, Waste Management Organisation)

Implications of licencing harmonisation

The fragmented waste management landscape operates across formal, semi-formal, and informal sectors often lacking proper licensing^{13,15} and dependent on illegal labour. This affects how discarded materials are processed and disposed of. A lack of consistent licencing impacts secondary material pricing and waste disposal practices, leading to a complex system influenced by differing preferences and economic values among businesses, residents, and industries. The situation is further complicated by the influx of imported waste, often inaccurately labelled and mishandled.

Households are crucial channels for waste disposal, using services like free collection by NGOs, drop-off points for recyclables, and informal waste pickers. Household choices are often influenced by personal convenience and financial incentives.

“

At home...I don't really do really proper recycling. But I do tell my maid and say, plastics, zinc, that kind, I'll ask her to sort it out. Then... because we have a relative who collects these items, then I'll collect it and once I have a lot, I'll call them and ask them to take it.

(Saddie, 56, self-employed, extended family household)

A lack of licencing and effective sanctions is thought to contribute to the flourishing of illegal and semi-legal activities, causing mismanagement of plastic waste. The informal sector selectively collects high-value plastics (e.g. PET, HDPE, LDPE and PP), while formal waste collection organisations often collaborate with informal actors, including waste pickers, to improve material recovery rates. Illegal activities, including dumping and unauthorised recycling, are widespread because of poor enforcement and low waste disposal fees.

The issue escalated following China's 2018 ban on plastic waste imports, causing a surge in imported waste that further fuelled illegal practices^{13, 47}. Furthermore, organised crime had infiltrated the industry, leading to some legal disposal sites paying protection money to cartels.

“

...we do have informal sector or informal side where collectors are the ones who go to the house to house and send it to recycle centre where it's worth it for them as when they have volume then they get more money so like individual houses you won't get much out of your own consumption you need to pull from a lot of house[s] then you can get money worth talking about...

(Hashim, Assistant Manager, Waste Management Organization)

Opportunities

Based on the challenges identified above, to support a shift to more sustainable plastic packaging use and disposal, four opportunities emerged.

OPPORTUNITY 1: REDUCE CONSUMPTION OF SINGLE-USE PLASTICS

- + Consumer empowerment
- + Reduce plastic packaging use
- + Awareness training

OPPORTUNITY 2: ENHANCING CONSUMER EDUCATION ON RECYCLING PRACTICES

- + Clearer labelling
- + Public awareness campaigns
- + Accessible resources

OPPORTUNITY 3: IMPROVE MATERIAL QUALITY BY REDUCING CONTAMINATION

- + Education and Training
- + Improve collection and sorting
- + Collaboration to address waste material mismanagement
- + Supporting a circular economy
- + Recognising informal recyclers

OPPORTUNITY 4: IMPROVE DATA COLLECTION AND TRANSPARENCY FROM RECYCLING COLLECTION FACILITIES

- + Staff training
- + Data transparency

Opportunity 1: Reduce consumption of single-use plastics

Reuse, repurposing and reduction of plastic food containers and bags can contribute to reducing the consumption of single-use plastics. Consumers adopt innovative reuse and repurposing practices within households but struggle to avoid the volume of plastic purchased and provided at supermarkets.

To encourage reduction, the following activities can be undertaken.

CONSUMER EMPOWERMENT

For households:

- + Support community forums that share reuse and repurposing practices for plastic packaging.
- + Support local farmers' market to access plastic packaging free food.

For retailers and supermarkets:

- + Ask customers if they would like additional packaging (e.g. rather than providing plastic bags).

REDUCE PLASTIC PACKAGING USE

For households:

- + Support households to bring reusable shopping bags and encourage them to ask the question as to whether the plastic packaging is necessary before purchasing a product.

For retailers and supermarkets:

- + Review and identify food products that can be sold without packaging and determine which genuinely require an additional LDPE bag.

AWARENESS TRAINING

- + Supermarket staff could be trained to identify when packaging is unnecessary and make informed choices about packaging requirements²⁴, such as determining which products do not need an additional LDPE bag.

Balancing the reuse and reduction of plastic packaging, at the same time as maintaining food quality and safety, needs to be considered. Adopting this action could assist with tackling overconsumption of plastic packaging with households, with supermarkets playing an integral role to support the elimination and eradication of unnecessary single-use plastics as laid out in the MPSR.

Opportunity 2: Enhancing consumer education on recycling practices

Education and better access to knowledge are crucial in addressing these issues. Consumers often struggle with proper recycling, particularly for plastic packaging, which frequently lacks clear disposal instructions.

CLEAR LABELLING

- + Mandating standardised, easy-to-understand recycling symbols and disposal instructions on all packaging, especially plastics.

PUBLIC AWARENESS CAMPAIGNS

- + Launching widespread co-created educational campaigns to inform consumers about good recycling practices and the environmental impacts of improper disposal.
- + Campaigns should correspond to local recycling specifications and include recycling outcomes (e.g. the proportion successfully recycled/or product it was used for).

ACCESSIBLE RESOURCES

- + Improving access to local recycling services and facilities, accompanied by detailed guides on how to use them effectively.

Such initiatives have the potential to support and equip households to separate waste more effectively, rebuild trust in waste management systems, and ultimately reduce the volume of recyclable materials ending up in general waste streams.

Opportunity 3: Improve material quality by reducing contamination

Community drop-off centres and recycling centres play an integral role in managing recyclable materials. Contaminated materials - whether improperly sorted or unclean - compromise the efficiency of the recycling process, which can lead to higher costs, downcycling, and the diversion of valuable materials to landfill or illegal dumpsites. Addressing these issues at the point of collection and processing is vital for improving recycling outcomes and supporting MPSR to reduce plastic and circular economy agendas.

Suggestions to reduce contamination include:

EDUCATION & TRAINING

For households:

- + Utilise community drop-off centres as sites to provide information to their consumers on the importance of cleaning and properly sorting recyclables to reduce contamination at source. Clear instructions on how to clean and the importance of categorisation will further help consumers make informed choices.

Waste Collectors, Contractors and Recycling Centre Staff:

- + Provide training on the environmental and economic impact of material contamination on a recycling process (downcycling), and guidance on recognising what material quality/conditions can be accepted.

IMPROVE COLLECTION AND SORTING:

- + Community drop-off centres to distribute transparent bags to consumers for collecting recyclables to reduce contamination and improve inspection efficiency. Partner with local governments or businesses to subsidise or supply transparent bags at low or no cost customer.
- + Create incentive-based initiatives, such as discounts or rewards, to encourage consumers to properly clean and separate recyclables.
- + Equip collection and sorting facilities with user-friendly and clearly labelled containers for waste segregation to streamline the sorting process.

COLLABORATION TO ADDRESS PLASTIC WASTE MISMANAGEMENT:

- + Foster further collaboration that brings together contractors, subcontractors, waste management companies, government to discuss challenges that lead to mismanagement. Time constraints, limited budgets, material value, landfill fees and cost of recycling versus dumping are topics that could be discussed.

SUPPORTING A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

- + Manufacturers should work closely with recyclers to design products that are easier to recycle, using mono materials, easy to clean, or recyclable without excessive contamination (e.g. tackling issues with multilayered packaging).
- + Promoting closed-loop systems where manufacturers reuse their own materials or partner with recyclers to get higher quality recyclables back into the production process.

RECOGNISING INFORMAL RECYCLERS

- + Develop collaborations between the Waste Pickers Alliance, formal material recycling facilities, and waste collectors to recognise their role in the recycling eco-system (e.g. collected for recycling rate and environmental benefits), create fair compensation for materials collected to ensure stable and reliable income that does not put any informal worker at a disadvantage.

The challenges of contamination and material quality are central to the success of recycling and reuse systems. Through enhancing education and training, improving collections and sorting, and supporting collaborations across different stakeholders, there is a potential for contamination to be reduced and higher quality materials be collected.

Opportunity 4: Improve data collection and transparency from recycling centres

Missing data on potentially recyclable materials and those that were recycled is problematic for recycling centres when introducing incentives and applying for funding.

To address these challenges, centres could:

STAFF TRAINING

- + Educate staff on data collection, reporting and recording.

DATA TRANSPARENCY

- + Make data publicly available to the flow and fates of plastic packaging.

Collecting robust data and being transparent could contribute to knowledge and expertise being shared and improve consumer trust by identifying where discarded plastic packaging ends up.

Implications for the Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap

Phase out unnecessary single-use plastics.

25% of post-consumer plastic packaging to be recycled by 2025.

100% recyclability of plastic packaging.

15% average recycled content.

76% collected for-recycling rate.

Post-consumer halal rPET standard by 2022.

Our research is aligned to support the ambitions of Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap 2021-2030 by developing insights regarding challenges and opportunities to reduce household consumption of plastic packaging, improved recycling practices, recapture higher quality materials and perceptions about consumer resistance and waste workers' practices.

We have generated open access resources that can be utilised to support further research and help business leaders and policy makers to think about consumer and waste management practices, to support greener ambitions and sustainable solutions. Our activities are detailed in the table below:

MALAYSIAN PLASTIC SUSTAINABILITY ROADMAP TARGETS	PPIPL Responses				OUTCOMES & RESOURCES See Link
	ACTIONS	CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED	OPPORTUNITIES IDENTIFIED		
Phase out unnecessary single-use plastics	Obtained detailed insights into consumer behaviour and from waste management organisations and workers	Plastic packaging overconsumption Plastics delayed from entering waste streams	Reduce consumption of single-use plastics	Enhancing consumer education on recycling practices	8 organisations and 10 households took part in this study
		Lack of clear guidance about waste practices Infrastructure for plastic recycling			
25% of post-consumer plastic packaging to be recycled	Create guidance for post-consumption organisations	Capturing quality plastic packaging recyclables	Improve material quality by reducing contamination	Improve data collection and transparency	Industry and policy: Household and waste management practices report 54 Degrees Not the enemy - Taking PPIPL international Public: Pilot project Malaysia infographic
100% recyclability of plastic packaging		Navigating the intricacies of regulated and unregulated practices			
15% average recycled content					
76% collected for recycling rate					
Post-consumer halal rPET standard by 2022	Out of scope ²				

Future Research

From conducting our small-scale investigations, three research agendas have emerged that could further support government ambitions to move towards a circular zero waste society.

1. Rethinking the consumer attitude behaviour gap. An in-depth examination to investigate how food plastic packaging is embedded in consumers day-to-day lives. Taking the food sector as an exemplar, this research would examine the whole packaging supply chain (production, consumption, post-consumption, waste disposal technologies and processes). This will be of interest to all stakeholders operating in formal, semi-formal, and informal circular value chains to support behavioural shifts in reducing plastic packaging consumption and enhance reuse, repurposing and recycling practices.

2. Circular material and social flows, fates, and frictions. A detailed investigation of the material and social flows, fates, and frictions of different plastic recycling streams. The aim would be to understand the efficacy of these material flows, trade-offs (people, planet, profit) and implications for supporting the recapture of high-quality materials to achieve the recycle content and collection rate ambitions of the MPSR. This study would require a transdisciplinary approach that considered the social, environmental, and economic impacts of different plastic recycling streams.

3. Digital monitoring of material flows. Further work could explore the role and impact of technologies used to monitor and report on collection and recycling rates to better appreciate the volumes and contributions from all marketplace actors (consumers, value chain and waste management) to the recapture of materials. This study could look at the intended and unintended consequences of surveillance, improve data collection and transparency, and ensure inclusivity.

Next Steps

The momentum generated by the Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap must be harnessed. The PPIPL Team welcomes the opportunity to further expand these research ideas with funders, partners and collaborators (both existing and new), capitalising on the immediate opportunities in Malaysia to address the country specific challenges facing this growing economy in the coming decade.

This pilot project has provided a glimpse of the potential for meaningful action and offers timely insight into the necessary direction for progress. As the climate crisis intensifies, the time for action is now.

References and Endnotes

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Appendix

The tables below provide information about household and waste management participants, note all participants and organisations have been given pseudonyms.

Household research participants

HH	HH DESCRIPTION	LOCALITY	GENDER	NAME	PARTICIPANT OCCUPATION	AGE	ETHNICITY
1	Single person household - lone person of age 50+	Kajang	F	Sally	Self-employed	50	Chinese
2	Multiple household - members of household are not related (e.g. student accommodation)	Sunway	F	Ella	Student and self-employed	24	Indian
3	Extended family household - parents, children and grandparent(s) or other relative(s) living together in rural area	Kajang	F	Amy	Teacher	46	Chinese
4	Three to five persons household - nuclear family, 2 parents and 1 or 2 children	Bukit Jalan	M	Rumi	IT specialist	50	Chinese
5	Two to three persons household - lone parent with 1 or 2 dependent children	Bukit Jalil	F	Tina	Part-time lecturer	47	Chinese

HH	HH DESCRIPTION	LOCALITY	GENDER	NAME	PARTICIPANT OCCUPATION	AGE	ETHNICITY
6	Three to five persons household - nuclear family, 2 parents and 1 or 2 children	Shah Alam	F	Naomi	Admin assistant	58	Malay
7	Two to three persons household - lone parent with 1 or 2 independent children	Taman Sri Putra	F	Delanie	Teacher	47	Chinese
8	Single person household - lone adult under 35, unmarried without children	Petaling Jaya	F	Arlene	Student	30	Chinese
9	Two persons household - couples without children	Semenyih	M	Jared	Lecturer	35	Chinese
			F	Lola	Banker	35	
10	Extended family household - parents, children and grandparent(s) or other relative(s) living together in rural area	Sabak Bernam	F	Saddie	Self-employed	56	Chinese

Waste management research participants

ORGANISATION	OPERATIONS	NO.	NAME AND ROLE
Formal Circular Economy Agenda Organisation	Residential, commercial, and institutional waste collection, separation, storage, and material selling	1	Senen - Head of Facilities
Formal Waste Management Organisation	Residential waste collection and transporting collected recyclables	2	Khari - Executive, Project Delivery
		1	Daim - Project Delivery Assistant
		1	Emran - Assistant Project Delivery Manager
		1	Hashim - Assistant Manager
		1	Barzin - General Manager
Semi-formal Recycling Centre I	Waste recycling facility, storage and material selling, "trash for cash"	1	Brasen - Head of Facilities
		1	Mahadi - Assistant Manager
		1	Panjang - Material Separation
		3	Bisaam - Material Separation
		2	Raffi & Badri - Material Separation
		1	Rashidi - Machine Operator
		4	Ridhwan, Ishraaq, Fariq & Imran - Material Separation
Formal Community Drop-off Centre	Recycling collection point for residential recyclable waste, drop-off station, visitor centre with educative events, "trash for cash"	1	Jabar - Facility Operative
		1	Hadees - Assistant Manager
Sanitary Landfill		1	Laki - Head of Landfill Operation
		1	Shalika - Assistant to the Head of Landfill Operation
Semi-formal Recycling Centre II	Waste recycling facility, storage and material selling, "trash for cash"	1	Bukhari - Material Separation
		1	Kassim - Gate Guard/ Site Supervisor
Formal Recycling Centre III	Recycling collection point for residential recyclable waste, "trash for cash"	1	Uwais - Gate Guard/Site Supervisor
Illegal Dumpsite	Non-licenced informal dumpsite	0	No interviews

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